

A Study on the Production of Strain and Pin Types Porcelain Insulator

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Abstract

In this work, determination of physico-chemical properties and mechanical properties of clays, and the chemical analysis of clays, feldspar, and quartz were carried out. Different siliceous body mixtures by using indigenous raw materials were sintered at 1225°C in the shuttle kiln. Their physico-chemical, mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties were measured. Suitable processed glaze was applied to bodies. The comparative study between strength of glazed and unglazed bodies were also carried out. Based on the overall results, the best body composition was selected to prepare strain and pin type insulators. Prepared pin and strain insulators were tested by visual inspection, dry power frequency withstand voltage test, wet power frequency withstand voltage test, lightning impulse voltage test, power frequency puncture test, temperature cycle test, and thermal shock test (IEC 383 standard).

Introduction

Porcelain is made of all-natural raw materials; quartz, feldspar and kaolin. It possesses all the major characteristics of technical ceramics. Increasing demands on ceramic components for electric power generation and distribution systems and mechanical engineering uses have led to improve material properties and the development of new manufacturing methods. It is important to understand the physical, mechanical and thermal properties of porcelain bodies that are formed by slip casting, extruding and pressing. Porcelain insulators are widely used in electrical applications such as power transmission and distribution. There are a lot of insulator types including, disc insulator, pin insulator, post insulator, spool and guy strain insulator, bus insulator, etc. A pin insulator consists of a nonconducting material such as porcelain, glass, plastic, polymer, or wood that is formed into a shape that will isolate a wire from a physical support (or "pin") on a telegraph, utility pole or other structure, provide a means to hold the insulator to the pin, and provide a means to secure the conductor to the insulator. A strain insulator is an electrical insulator that is designed to work in mechanical tension (strain) to withstand the pull of a suspended electrical wire or cable.

Materials and Methodology

Materials

Locally available five clay materials: ball clay (Taungnaut) from Kyaukpadaung Township, Mandalay Region, ball clay (Yankintaung) from Minhla Township, Bago Region, china clay (Kanpauk) from Kyaukpadaung Township, Mandalay Region, china clay (Shwetaung) from Shwetaung Township, Bago Region, china clay (Yozayat) from Pakoku Township, Magwe Region were prepared for the preparation of porcelain. Feldspar from Tharzi Township, Mandalay Region was used as a flux material and quartz (Myeik) from Thanintharyi Region was used as filler. Feldspar, quartz, ball clay, dolomite, calcite, barium carbonate, Al₂O₃, MnO₂, Cr₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ were used as raw materials for glaze slip.

Methodology

Chemical Analysis of Local Raw Materials

Chemical compositions of raw clay minerals (SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MgO, CaO, Na₂O, K₂O and Loss on Ignition) were determined.

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Physico-Chemical Properties of Clay Materials

Color, shrinkage (drying shrinkage and firing shrinkage), water absorption, bulk density and apparent porosity of clays materials were determined.

Mechanical Properties of Clays

Automatic MOR Machine was used to find out the breaking load as well as the calculated dry Modulus of Rupture value directly.

Preparation of Siliceous Electrical Porcelain Bodies

Preparation Test Circular Bars

Slip for various bodies were prepared with composition as described in Table 1. 25% by weight of water was added to form the required consistency. The slip obtained was poured into POP molds to get round shaped test bars. The test bars were dried at 110°C for 12 h. Test circular bars were prepared with different body compositions (A, B, C, and D).

Preparation of Glaze Slip

Glaze was prepared according to the composition as shown in Table 2. The known weights of raw materials were put into a pot mill. Correct amount of water was added to the pot mill. The glaze was obtained after operating the pot mill for 48 h.

Sintering the Test Circular Bars at 1225°C

Circular bars (both glazed and unglazed) were sintered in the shuttle kiln. Six hours sintering was required to reach 300°C and 12 h for 600°C. Those were smoking period. Two hours was needed to 650°C and 6 h for 950°C. Two hours was required for 950°C - 1000°C and 6 h for 1000°C - 1225°C. The annealing time was 2 h and cooling time was 29 h. So the time for total firing cycle was 65 h.

Physico-Chemical Properties of Siliceous Porcelain Bodies

Physico-chemical properties of unglazed test circular bars (color, drying shrinkage, firing shrinkage, water absorption, bulk density and apparent porosity) were determined.

Mechanical Properties of Siliceous Porcelain Bodies

Mechanical properties of different bodies (glazed and unglazed) such as dry Modulus of Rupture (dry MOR) and fired Modulus of Rupture (fired MOR) were determined.

Determination of Thermal and Electrical Properties of Electrical Porcelains

Thermal diffusivities of opaque solid samples were determined by Flash method. Electrical resistivities of samples were measured by using an electrometer (1V-200V). The capacitance with the dielectric material is related to dielectric constant. The capacitances of the samples at various frequencies (100 Hz, 1000 Hz, 10000 Hz and 100000 Hz) were measured by using an LCR (Inductance, Capacitance and Resistance) meter.

Preparation of Strain and Pin Type Insulators and Tests

Body A was selected to prepare strain and pin insulators. The scanning electron microscope (6330LV) was used to observe microstructure of electrical porcelain, body A. Stepwise processing as shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9 were required to be done to prepare pin and strain insulators. Prepared insulators were tested by visual inspection, dry power frequency withstand voltage test, wet power frequency withstand voltage test, lightning impulse voltage test, power frequency puncture test, temperature cycle test, and thermal shock test (IEC 383 standard).

Table 1. Compositions of Siliceous Electrical Porcelain Bodies

No.	Body	Ball clay (TN) (% w/w)	Ball clay (YKT) (% w/w)	China clay (KP) (% w/w)	China clay (ST) (% w/w)	China clay (YZY) (% w/w)	Feldspar (TZ) (% w/w)	Quartz (Myeik) (% w/w)
1	A	-	35	-	20	-	30	15
2	B	-	20	-	-	22	35	23
3	C	-	30	15	-	15	25	15
4	D	5	18	6	-	13	38	20

TN= Taungnaut, YKT = Yankintaung, ST = Shwetaung, KP = Kanpauk, YZY = Yozayat, TZ = Tharzi

Table 2. Composition of Glaze for Siliceous Electrical Porcelains

No.	Materials	Composition (% w/w)
1	Dolomite	5
2	Calcite	5
3	Feldspar	47
4	Quartz	18
5	Ball clay (YKT)	10
6	BaCO ₃	3
7	Al ₂ O ₃	3
8	MnO ₂	5
9	Cr ₂ O ₃	1
10	Fe ₂ O ₃	2
	Total	100

Results and Discussion

Character of the raw materials is very important to obtain right body composition for good porcelain. Clays are chosen for the particular properties desired and are frequently blended to give the most favorable result. Ball clays have good contribution of workability, plasticity, and strength to the body in drying. Myanmar feldspars are potash feldspar and combined with silica veins. The finer grain size of quartz is also important to obtain better porcelain. The firing properties of greatest interest for ceramic are color, shrinkage, and porosity. It was found that, bulk densities of ball clays were higher than that of china clays. High dense clays would likely to be contained low water absorption. Porosity shows the percentage of pore volume against the total volume. Bulk density, water absorption, and apparent porosity are closely connected with each other and they are very important factors to judge the refractory quality. From the data in Table 5, it was observed that fired MOR was not depending on dry MOR and fired MOR of ball clays was higher than that of china clays. Thus, highly dense clays would have high mechanical strength.

Table 3. Results of Chemical Analysis of Raw Materials in Weight Percent

Material	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	LOI
Ball clay (TN)	66.38	20.36	4.70	0.05	1.23	0.03	2.50	4.75
Ball clay (YKT)	62.12	27.08	3.00	0.50	0.33	0.02	1.22	5.74
China clay (KP)	62.80	19.90	4.70	3.61	0.75	0.74	3.50	4.00
China clay (ST)	67.02	24.49	1.28	0.49	0.30	0.65	2.02	3.74
China clay (YZY)	58.18	35.36	1.74	0.91	0.63	0.55	0.84	2.25
Feldspar (TZ)	73.00	15.26	0.26	0.04	0.12	1.01	10.00	0.32
Quartz (Myeik)	97.07	2.03	0.08	0.14	0.08	0.03	0.51	0.06

Table 4. Physico-Chemical Properties of Circular Bars of Clay Materials

No.	Property	Ball clay (TN)	Ball clay (YKT)	China clay (KP)	China clay (ST)	China clay (YZY)
1	Particle size (mesh)	200	200	200	200	200
2	Firing temperature (°C)	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200
3	Firing color	brown	cream	light brown	cream	white
4	Firing cycle (h)	48	48	48	48	48
5	Drying shrinkage (%)	7.0	8.0	8.8	5.0	2.5
6	Firing shrinkage (%)	15.0	18.0	18.5	14.0	10.0
7	Total shrinkage (%)	22.0	26.0	27.3	19.0	12.5
8	Water absorption (% w/w)	3.3	2.6	4.6	8.8	11.3
9	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	2.6	2.5	2.3	2.3	2.0
10	Apparent porosity (% w/w)	8.5	1.5	8.4	3.0	7.5

Table 5. Mechanical Properties of Clays

No.	Property	Ball clay (TN)	Ball clay (YKT)	China clay (KP)	China clay (ST)	China clay (YZY)
1	Dry MOR (kg/cm ²)	16.6	15.4	32.5	7.4	8.7
2	Fired MOR (kg/cm ²)	302.3	450.5	300.9	105.5	197.8

Table 6 shows that, the body with highest bulk density occupied 2.4 g/cm³ and well densified objects were required to get good porcelains. 0% water absorption and 0% apparent porosity values were occurred with samples A, C, and D. An insulator must have 0% water absorption and 0% porosity. From Table 7, it was found that, MOR of sintered glazed samples were higher than the bodies without glaze. Body C of porcelain without glaze had the highest fired MOR whereas sample D with glaze had the highest fired MOR.

From Table 8, it can be seen that, body B was obtained as the highest thermal conductivity. The relative density of the samples was depended on the composition of the bodies. The highest electrical resistivity was occurred with samples A. Low electrical resistivity samples were not efficient to get reliable data for the dielectric constant. It was found from Table 8 that all porcelain samples were frequency dependent. Their dielectric

constant values were gradually decreased as the frequency was increased.

Table 6. Physico-Chemical Properties of Siliceous Electrical Porcelain

No.	Property	Body sintered at 1225°C			
		A	B	C	D
1	Firing cycle (hr)	65	65	65	65
2	Color	cream	cream	yellowish cream	cream
3	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	2.4	2.4	2.3	2.4
4	Water absorption (% w/w)	0	1.5	0	0
5	Apparent porosity (% w/w)	0	2.3	0	0
6	Drying shrinkage (%)	3.5	3.0	3.8	3.0
7	Firing shrinkage (%)	7.0	9.7	9.8	11.9
8	Total shrinkage (%)	10.5	12.7	13.6	14.9

Figure 1. Siliceous Electrical Unglazed and Glazed Porcelain Bodies

Figure 2. Samples of: (a) Over Glaze, (b) Match Glaze and (c) Under Glaze

Table 7. Mechanical Properties of Electrical Porcelains

Body	Sintered temperature (°C)	Modulus of rupture (kg/cm ²)		
		Before sintered	Sintered	Sintered with glaze
A	1225	20.0	773.0	992.4
B	1225	17.0	849.1	952.2
C	1225	23.0	991.2	1001.0
D	1225	17.0	800.2	1010.0

The experiments were carried out at High-tension Insulator Factory, Ministry of Industry, Chauk Township, Magwe Region.

Figure 3. Bending Strength of Unglazed and Glazed Electrical Porcelains

Table 8. Thermal Conductivity and Electrical Resistivity of Porcelains

Body	Sintered temp. (°C)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Thermal conductivity (W/m/K)	Electrical resistivity (Ωcm)
A	1225	2.4	1.6	2.47E+13
B	1225	2.4	1.8	11.1E+11
C	1225	2.3	1.6	1.01E+11
D	1225	2.4	1.7	3.02E+10

Table 9. Dielectric Constant of Electrical Porcelains

Body	Sintered temp. (°C)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Dielectric constant (Hz)			
			100	1000	10000	100000
A	1225	2.4	8.6	8.5	8.4	8.3
B	1225	2.4	12.1	9.0	8.0	7.8
C	1225	2.3	9.2	8.5	8.3	8.2
D	1225	2.4	8.7	8.3	8.2	8.2

Table 10. Dielectric Loss of Electrical Porcelains

Body	Sintered temp. (°C)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Dielectric constant (Hz)			
			100	1000	10000	100000
A	1225	2.4	0.0435	0.0162	0.0096	0.0090
B	1225	2.4	0.3550	0.1552	0.0508	0.0146
C	1225	2.3	0.1036	0.0390	0.0149	0.01206
D	1225	2.4	0.0334	0.0144	0.0102	0.0101

Data of Tables (8-10) were measured at Department of Frontier Materials, Graduate School of Engineering, Nagoya Institute of Technology, Japan.

In this research work, strain and pin insulators were prepared. Based on the overall evaluated results, the best body composition A was selected to prepare insulators. SEM micrograph of electrical porcelain A at 500x and 3000x are shown in Figure 6. The scattering in the values of the dielectric loss and the dielectric constant was smaller and the data was reliable. The relatively higher electron resistivity could be successfully achieved for this sample.

Figure 4. Dielectric constant vs frequency of siliceous electrical porcelains

Figure 5. Dielectric loss vs frequency of siliceous electrical porcelains

The results of all applicable tests for prepared insulators are presented in Table (11-17) and all passed the recommended tests.

Figure 6. SEM micrograph of Electrical Porcelain A (Sintered at 1225°C)

Table 11. Visual Inspection of Prepared Insulators

Type of insulator	No of specimen	Body composition	Description
Pin (11KV)	5	A	Good
Strain (230/440V)	5	A	Good

Table 12. Results of Dry Power Frequency Withstand Test

Type of insulator	No of specimen	Consecutive application voltage (KV)	Time interval of voltage application (min)	Description	
				Without assembly	With assembly
Pin (11KV)	4	60-65	3	no flash over	no flash over

Table 13. Results of Wet Power Frequency Test

Type of insulator	No of specimen	Applied withstand voltage (KV)	Time interval of voltage application (min)	Water condition		Remark
				Temperature (°C)	Resistivity (Ωm)	
Pin (11KV)	3	40	3	40	110	no flash over

Table 14. Results of Power Frequency Puncture Test

Type of insulator	Used insulating medium	Insulating medium temperature	Applied voltage (KV)	Time interval for voltage application (min)	Remark
Pin (11KV)	transformer oil	room temperature	110	3	withstand the applied voltage

Table 15. Results of Dry Lightning Impulse Voltage Test

Type of insulator	No of specimen	KV for standard impulse volt of 11 KV line	Impulse volt (KV)	Remark
Pin (11KV)	2	75	120	withstand the applied voltage

Table 16. Results of Temperature Cycle Test

Type of insulator	Time interval at 100°C (min)	Time interval at 30°C (min)	Time taken to transfer (sec)	Visual examination	Dry power frequency test	Temperature cycle test
Pin (11KV)	15	15	5	no craze	passed	passed
Strain (230/440V)	15	15	6	no craze	passed	passed

Table 17. Results of Thermal Shock Test

Type of insulator	Temperature in the hot air oven (°C)	Time interval in ice water (min)	Visual examination	Dry power frequency test	Thermal shock test
Pin (11KV)	100	2	no craze	passed	passed
Strain (230/440V)	100	2	no craze	passed	passed

The experiments from Tables (11) to (17) were carried out at High-tension Insulator Factory, Ministry of Industry, Chauk Township, Magwe Region.

Figure 7. Pin and Strain Insulators (a) before Sintering (b) after Sintering

Conclusions

For higher strength porcelain, a good transparency glassified bond should be build by using right proportion of silica and alumina. The workability of clay was influenced by the physical property. Thus clays were blended to obtain the most favorable results. Superior combination was also important to resist the coincidence forces. The degree of fineness of glaze particles and glaze thickness were affected on the strength of porcelain. Glazed porcelains were found to be higher strength than unglazed porcelains. It is very important to specify a glaze formula for any particular piece of porcelain ware to prevent crazing and to increase the overall strength. The relative density of the samples was depended on the composition of the samples, and it was estimated for prepared samples that the thermal conductivity and the resistivity increased with increasing the relative density of the samples.

The high-tension insulator must have good electrical properties as well as high mechanical strength. So, it was decided that body A was selected for preparing strain and pin insulators which were safe to use as insulators.

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Figure 8. Process Flow Diagram for Preparation of Pin Insulator

Figure 9. Process Flow Diagram for Preparation of Strain Insulator